

Treatment of Nature in Wilfred Owen's Trench Poetry : A Critical Study

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Abstract

Nature and its colourful reflections remain the perpetual source of romantic imagination and poetic creation. If we evaluate the history of English poetry from the Anglo-Saxon period to the first half of the nineteenth century, we get various shades and forms of nature, representing the various moods, feelings and longings of human beings. As a matter of fact, Poetry itself has taken birth from the permanent and infinite book of Nature. Before the rise of industrial and urban culture, Nature had been always depicted in its positive and benevolent form. Shakespeare, Wordsworth, Shelley, Keats and others survived with their immortal poetry only due to their pure devotion to nature in their creative writings. This trend of nature poetry got changed completely from the last decades of nineteenth century. With the outbreak of the Great war, the pure, serene and benevolent natural surroundings got devastated and the urban, sordid culture completely damaged the peaceful rural culture. The English soldiers in the muddy, brown battlefield used to pacify themselves with the memories of beautiful green natural surroundings of their homeland. Wilfred Owen, the young soldier poet of the Great war, wrote much on the devastated form of nature, and his war poems reflect the bleak and traumatic form of Nature. This research paper intends to highlight the disillusionment of Owen in particular and the English soldiers in general, caused by the growing hostility between Nature and men during the ongoing war.

Keywords

Nature, Romantic Imagination, benevolent and green natural surroundings, battlefield, disillusionment, Hostility.

Introduction

Wilfred Owen has been the most celebrated soldier-poet of the poetry, written during the First World War. Before joining the war as a soldier, he used to write poetry also, but these poems were romantic and sensuous in temper with beautiful images, taken from Nature. While fighting as a soldier in the battlefield and cold trenches, Owen realized the inhumanity of war which he perceived in the devastated form of the natural surroundings. His sensitive mind became highly disturbed to experience the savagery of war which he had never imagined. Unlike Rupert Brooke, he started denouncing the atrocious form of war which killed not only the peace of mankind but also the serenity or spirit of Nature. He describes the gloom and hopelessness of the natural landscape to co-relate it to the depression and anxiety of the soldiers, living in the dark, cold trenches. His poems, dealing with the hostility between aggressive men and Nature, were written mostly in the military hospitals through his ruminations over the horrible war experiences. That's why, Wilfred Owen, along with his mentor, siegfried Sassoon, are treated as the apostles of world peace and Universal brotherhood. They refused to write heroic poems of war which were written to encourage the young English people for joining the war.

Before joining the English army in the Artists Rifles on 21 October, 1915, he had been working as a private tutor, teaching English and French at the Berlitz School of Languages in Bordeaux in French, but he returned England as soon as the First World War broke out to join the English army. After his rigorous training for seven months at Hare Hall Camp in Essex, Owen had been commissioned as a second lieutenant in the Manchester Regiment. The romantic and imaginative mind of Owen, at first, didn't accept the vulgar and unsentimental life-style of an English soldier, but slowly and gradually he adapted himself to that rough-tough life for the sake of his survival and his service to his country, England. While fighting at the Front, Owen suffered both the physical and mental trauma several times and for his speedy recovery, he had been admitted to the military hospital frequently. Once, Owen suffered much due to shell shock or neurasthenia when a trench mortar shell blasted closely to him. Owen was sent to Craiglockhart War Hospital

in Edinburgh where he came across another great soldier-poet, Sassoon who motivated him to write the ugly realities of war through his poems. After his posting for light regimented duties in North Yorkshire and then in March 1918 at Ripon, Owen composed and revised a number of his war poems, dealing with the wastage of youth and natural surroundings.

Owen returned to the active military service, to the Frontline, in August, 1918 and he was awarded the Military Cross for his exemplary courage and leadership posthumously on 15 February, 1919. Owen was killed with a stray bullet on 4 November, 1918 just before a week of the Armistice which closed the prolonged First World War. Only five of Owen's poetry were published during his life time and after his death, most of his poems were collected in different volumes by his relatives and poet-friends like Sassoon, Edith Sitwell, and Edmund Blunden. With their preface for publication, even though Owen has been criticized by some English poets as an escapist for his anti-war sentimental poems yet he became the most popular war-poet who depicted the devastated humanity and nature through his pictorial poetry. With his own unique style, the main purpose of my research paper is to expose the reality of the devastating war and its harmful and damaging effect on the purity of natural surroundings.

Objective of study

The critical study of Wilfred Owen's trench poetry has following objectives to justify :

1. The inhumanity of the Great war to Society and Nature ;
2. The reaction – response to the devastated Nature by the fighting soldiers ;
3. The incompatibility between the trench war-poetry and Nature ;
4. The validity of Owen's poetry for the post-War generation.

Review of Literature

When Wilfred Owen's poems were published posthumously, several reviews, including the great war-poet, Henry Newbolt called Owen's poetry as "the poetic work of a broken man". He commented further that "these shells shocked."⁽⁶⁾ Contrary to Henry Newbolt's observations, John Middleton Murry appreciated Owen's trench poetry as the records of high courage and human sympathy: "The poetry is in the pity'. Whatever the new generation of poets may think or say, Owen had the secret in those words. The source of all enduring poetry lies in an intense and overwhelming emotion" ⁽⁷⁾ Similarly, Carter and McRae appreciated Owen's trench poetry for questioning "the necessity of war, stressed the common humanity of both sides in the war, and linked the fatality of the deaths of the individual soldiers to the cosmic indifference of a world from which God was conspicuously absent"⁽⁸⁾. Recently, Feminist critics reviewed Owen's poetry as an indictment of Patriarchal culture because his trench poetry used to reflect Nature as feminine beings, devastated by the Masculine war. In this context, Jennifer Brench comments that Owen's anti-war poetry shows us "how any authoritarian patriarch is likely to become corrupted by power as well as by Pride" ⁽⁹⁾ Even the Marxist and socialist critics approve Owen's sympathetic poetry for its proper use of political purpose and for its advocacy to glorify the lively relationship between the commonman and Nature.

Main Text**Exposition**

Owen's letters to his mother and poems composed during 1917-18 clearly indicated his shaken faith in Christianity and the political machinery of England, and naturally he tried to revise and reform his own Christian beliefs in the light of the soldier's sufferings and his own conscience. Owen wrote his sonnet '1914' in 1914 about the glories of war, but he revised his sonnet in 1917 by saying that war has changed the autumn into a dark cold winter when there is no light, life and warmth in the natural surroundings. It appears to him that the whole of Europe is engulfed with the destructive force of the tornado, violence and bloodshed started by Germany. Progress of humanity, nature and arts has been consumed by the chaotic and bloody forces of war. But now, for us, wild winter, and the need of sowings for new spring, and blood for seed. ⁽¹⁾

The ideas of Spring and Summer as 'bloomed' and 'blaze', indicate the productive phases of Pre-war nature and its seasons, but in the post-war era, Spring and Summer are overshadowed with gloomy war. He expands the idea of this natural cycle of seasons by suggesting that its bud and blossoms of Spring and Summer can be restored by sowing the blood-seeds of the soldiers. Owen's view of the war as an inevitable cycle of death and renewal on the one hand and the human civilization with its Spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter is typical of the Decadent movement.

Owen's poem 'The Show' was drafted in November 1917, motivated by the prize-winning war novel, *Le Feu*. This poem is written against the backdrop of a battlefield, during an assault between British and German troops, full of mud and water in which the figures appear, all blinded and borne down with filth like the dreadful castaways of shipwreck. The whole battlefield appears hopeless and unproductive, with soldiers creeping like thin caterpillars. The poem 'The Show' ends abruptly on a note of remorse and guilty conscience because while

surveying the barren, desolate battlefield with the inhuman, insect-like condition of soldiers, Owen takes the responsibility for the plight and horror of the battlefield :

And He, picking a manner of worm, which Half had hid, Its bruises in the earth, but crawled on Further.⁽²⁾

Owen states that war is unnatural to society and Nature, and in 'Exposition', seems hostile to those who get involved in the devastating war. Owen concludes the poem by highlighting his personal feelings of terror and death that permeates the battlefield of Scarborough. Through his conversation with Sassoon at Craiglockhart, Owen developed a space, an artistic and philosophic space in his mind to process the sufferings he had seen and was seeing around the battlefield. He was also made the editor of The Hospital Literary magazine, 'The Hydra' in which he published the first two poems of his own anonymously, entitled 'Song of Songs' and 'The Next War'.

'Exposure', has been appreciated as one of Owen's carefully meditated war poems, with its haunting verbal and descriptive beauty with smack of typical Keatsian sensuousness. At the same time, "Exposure" proves to be an unusual Great War poem by any standard, because its details insinuate that in the battlefield a soldier has to fight not as much with other soldiers as with the hostile natural elements. The soldiers have to face extreme cold and frostbite both in the unprotected trenches and in the open battlefield. The merciless icy wind constantly beating and knocking the soldiers with its pointed snowflakes. Owen prescribes the elements of nature more hostile to the exposed soldiers than the German soldiers hiding in their camp. The horrifying winter landscape of the battlefield and its piercing sound reminds the poet the twitching agonies of the dying men on the barbed wire. Even the bullets and its tumble sound are not as deadly as the flakes of the freezing air. Some of the soldiers imagine that they are basking in the warmth of the sun, lying in a field filled with flowers and birds. Again, they console themselves with the warm unprotected indoor of their home, with snow and winter outside. Some soldiers anticipate their death with frozen wind and snow and others think that they would die of freezing cold when they dig the graves for the dead soldiers. It is rightly said that 'the contrasting Keatsian richness in stanzas five and six is partly licensed by the fact that under such an assault, the soldiers driven in upon themselves, become immersed in a form of other - worldly hallucination in which they recall images of home, but images now nightmarishly corrupted by their sense of being universally alienated.'⁽³⁾

In his poem 'Futility' written in 1918, Owen describes the meaningless and pathetic death of a soldier, amidst the freezing snow in France. Some of the soldiers put the death, frozen body of the soldiers in the warmth of the sun, but even the life-giver Sun does not rouse him to life. Through the frozen body of the soldier, the poet mourns not only for the pathetic death of the soldier but also the futility of the sun, the life giver against the power of the death. We get the repetition of the word, 'the Sun' because it is the vitality of nature. He wonders the helplessness and hopelessness of the power of the sun which surrenders its reviving power to death. In one of his letters to his mother, Owen describes the numbness of the snowy trenches and the glare of the sun outside in the battlefield, but the soldiers avoid going outside in the field for fear of crashing shells.

Owen's last great war poem was written in the summer of 1918, and he revised this poem between July and September, but he did not complete his revisions. 'Spring Offensive' incorporates memories of the hurricane barrage at Fayet in April 1917, Although some of the details are altered to resonate with literary tradition. Long ago, in his early enthusiasm for Keats, Wilfred had hoped for a vision like those granted to old dreamers on May Morn's, and his last finished poem is set in May, Shropshire - like landscape where he felt native a teacher of morality as felt by the great native poet William Wordsworth. Buttercups and brambles during the spring season appear to be blessings and delightful peace, but the offensive is against the spring season as well as lies in it. When the soldiers attack on their own mother earth, nature responds with necessary fury until the air is once again cool and peaceful. The soldiers are heroes, and their heroism is not the absurd naive value admired by story tellers. Curious pieces are brushed aside in the last stanza. Only soldiers who have entered hell as living men can know the truth, and they keep their Secret.⁽⁴⁾

According to Owen, men wait to launch an attack in the spring landscape, apparently soothed by nature. Then they go over the top into battle, which involves a rejection of what is natural. Immediately nature seems to turn against them. The final stanza with a question is supposed to be written as the last piece of poetry by Owen, and on this ground it is also believed that this last poem contains memories Not only of 1917 barrage at Fayette, but also of the catastrophic charge of the 16th Lancashire Fusiliers at Jancourt on 2nd October, 1918; a disaster that Wilfred

had to watch at close quarters. In this poem Owen raises a number of questions, as life with death, peace with war, or belief with skepticism. Owen wonders at the rushing soldiers into hell-like German trenches only to achieve victory by evil actions or the worst form of inhumanities and if they survive, they are amazed to crawl out alive and be able to breathe the cool air once more. The poet wants to put an end to all these hellish activities by complaining about them to the comrades, who planned these things against God and nature.

The main theme of Owen's poetry is the 'pity of war' and the untold truth of war, based on his exposure of the inhumanity of the mechanized warfare. Owen uses nature in his poetry extensively to reveal how men were degraded at war due to their poor treatment and their surroundings' conditions, belittling their entire being to that of an insect or an animal, as depicted both in *The Show* and *Spring Offensive*. Nature is presented as providing both a sense of tranquility during rest at war, but equally it seemed in a place of such desolate isolation from civilized life and it seemed that even nature acted against the soldiers. Nature is used in *Spring offensive* more directly, building scenic imagery. From an objective point of view against this fierce backdrop of battle and fury, while in *The Show* nature is used in a more metaphorical sense used to describe the physical and mental state of men at war. In his famous anti-war poem, containing the theme of 'the pity of war', entitled, '*Mental Cases*', Owen describes the abnormal conditions of insane soldiers whose minds get deranged with the gruesome battlefield and its chemical warfare. Through the psychoanalytical description of these insane soldiers, Owen sets the poem in twilight which reflects the soft light between day and night to indicate how the men's minds seem to exist somewhere between life and death. This psychological trauma is aggravated with the look of the soldiers as beings of purgatorial shadows. Instead of being living persons with energy and hope, these men simply exist. Owen compares the 'sunlight' to a 'blood-smear' across the sky. This simile of 'sunlight' suggests their whole world, smeared with blood. Even when the night comes, it is blood-like black, ravishing their peace of mind. The repetition of 'blood' shows that they cannot forget the great mass of bodies they had to wonder through. The mention of the word 'Dawn', like a bleeding wound means that everyday comes with the Painful memories of bloodshed in the battlefield, and that it would never start a new peaceful life for them.

Conclusion

Before Wilfred Owen, most of the English Soldier-poets wrote in favour of war, because war had been a symbol of patriotism and nationalism. It was Owen who dared to challenge the notion of war as a form of patriotism and nationalism. To expose the savagery of war, Owen highlighted the perverted form of nature and its cycles of seasons. He means to say that if human beings do not care for the health and beauty of Nature, it would also show its insensitive nature to the human world. In such of his poems, *Exposure, 1914, Song of Songs* and *Mental Cases*, the 'cold winter' and the 'old spring' haunt the poetic mood of the poet and his fellow soldiers. Even in the spring season, the warmth and colour of youthful spring seem to be dampened by the lingering coldness of the winter season. The muddy form of soldiers, living in the trenches, appear to be brown, poisonous worms, coming from the dark holes of the earth. The fragrance of the fruits and flowers is replaced with the caustic smell of the bomb-shells. The whole green areas of the war zone seem to be arid and half-burnt due to the dropping of the poisonous gas-shells. Owen's poems may also be appreciated as a serious form of ecocriticism because he makes people realize the ecological devastation, caused by the intensity of war. Wordsworth had denounced urbanization and industrialization as the chief enemies of the productive natural surroundings, but Owen moved a step further and showed how Nature became hostile to the war-prone and aggressive mankind. Whenever Owen and his soldier friends anticipated a carefree, blissful life, away from the cold and cramping battlefield, they always imagined themselves singing and flying high in the clear, blue sky, very much like the chirping birds of the green surroundings. Owen's poetic faculty has been appreciated by Edmund Blunden in these words: "Owen was one of the few spokesmen of the ordinary fighting man... people heard for the first time the articulate voice of rebellion"⁽⁵⁾.

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